

ELIXIR All ExCo 2026

Report on annual hybrid meeting

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DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.19387149](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19387149)

Background

The ELIXIR Platforms Executive Committees (ExCos) provide strategic leadership for the Technology and Science components of the ELIXIR Scientific Programme. They oversee the development and delivery of Commissioned Services, contribute to work plan design, ensure cross-Platform coordination, and support alignment with the governance structures of ELIXIR, including the Heads of Nodes (HoN), the Scientific Advisory Board (SAB), and the ELIXIR Board.

The All ExCo hybrid meeting took place on 10–11 February 2026 in Barcelona, Spain, as part of a co-located ELIXIR meeting. The meeting occurred at a pivotal point in the 2024–2028 programme cycle, with preparation underway for the 2027–2028 work plans and the mid-term review by the Scientific Advisory Board. It also provided the first opportunity for structured reflection on the next ELIXIR Scientific Programme (2029–2033).

The objectives of the meeting were threefold: to onboard newly appointed ExCo members and clarify governance roles and responsibilities; to consolidate and refine the draft 2027–2028 Platform work plans, including cross-Platform and cross-tier coordination; and to prepare strategically and logistically for the 2026 mid-term review and the longer-term programme consultation process.

Event Format and Participation

The meeting was held primarily in person, with selected participants joining remotely. Attendees included Platform ExCo members from Compute, Data, Interoperability, Tools, and Training, as well as ELIXIR Hub representatives (the ELIXIR Director, CTO, Programme Managers, Science Officers), and current as well as outgoing ExCo members. The agenda combined onboarding, plenary presentations, structured work plan discussions, and open strategic debate.

The format enabled both detailed discussion of Platform-specific activities and broader cross-cutting reflection on ELIXIR structures, funding models, and community engagement.

Event Content

The first session focused on onboarding and governance context. Newly appointed ExCo members were introduced, followed by a presentation and discussion of ELIXIR governance structures, including the role of the Board in approving work plans and budgets, the responsibilities of the Director and Hub Operations, the advisory function of the Heads of Nodes, and the review role of the Scientific Advisory Board. Particular emphasis was placed on the ExCo remit within Commissioned Services, including coordination, strategy development, reporting responsibilities, and quality control of deliverables. Discussion addressed the balance between acting as national representatives and as Platform stewards, the degree of bottom-up versus top-down planning, and the appropriate level of ExCo engagement in external funding opportunities.

The remainder of Day 1 was dedicated to refining the strategic overview and prioritisation for the 2027–2028 work plans. The financial envelope for this period, a little reduced relative to 2024–2026 as a result of inflationary pressures on budgets, framed the discussion and reinforced the need for prioritisation. Each Platform presented draft strategic objectives. The Compute Platform emphasised federated and hybrid cloud services, integration with AI Factories and EuroHPC, sensitive data processing, and alignment with EOSC Federation developments. The Data Platform outlined priorities around multi-omics brokering, credit and provenance frameworks, scalable curation, AI-readiness, and strengthening the CDR¹/EDD²/ECD³ ecosystem. The Interoperability Platform focused on consolidating the FAIR RDM ecosystem, refining FAIR assistance and assessment mechanisms, and deepening cross-Platform integration. The Tools Platform presented its continued development of the Research Software Ecosystem centred on the bio.tools registry and associated services including benchmarking, and reproducible workflows, while the Training Platform highlighted the expansion of registry usage and FAIR assessment of training materials.

Cross-Platform discussion centred on identifying a limited number of high-priority collaborative tasks and the importance of working with ELIXIR's Communities. Participants emphasised the importance of embedding cross-Platform elements within Platform work plans, ensuring explicit commitment of effort and deliverables, and aligning activities with Science Tiers and Communities. The need to strengthen coordination mechanisms, facilitated by Programme Managers, Science Officers, Platform Leads and Technical Coordinators, was recognised as critical for avoiding duplication and ensuring coherence.

Day 2 focused on preparation for the mid-term review by the Scientific Advisory Board, scheduled for June 2026. The group discussed presentation structure, material to be shared in advance, and the importance of mapping achievements clearly to the 2024–2028 Scientific Programme. There was consensus that concise structured summaries should be provided in advance, with presentations designed to prioritise clarity, demonstrable impact, and

¹ ELIXIR Core Data Resources, <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/core-data-resources>

² ELIXIR Deposition Databases, <https://elixir-europe.org/platforms/data/elixir-deposition-databases>

³ ELIXIR Community Databases, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17288942>

cross-Platform connections, leaving substantial time for questions and discussion. The review was framed as an opportunity for strategic input rather than a purely formal checkpoint.

The final session initiated discussion of the 2029–2033 Scientific Programme. Participants reflected on structural elements that persist across programme cycles, including Nodes, Platforms, Communities, and Science Tiers, and debated how consultation processes should be structured. Key issues included the degree of alignment between Platforms and Science Tiers, uneven engagement between Communities and Platforms, the influence of funding structures on collaboration patterns, and the challenge of ensuring meaningful user engagement. The role of Communities as ambassadors and conduits to external users was emphasised, alongside concerns that insufficient responsiveness or structural incentives could weaken these links.

Outcomes and Conclusion

The 2026 All ExCo meeting provided alignment on governance roles and clarified expectations regarding ExCo responsibilities within Commissioned Services and cross-Platform coordination. Strategic priorities and potential activities in the 2027–2028 work plans were refined in light of budget constraints and governance timelines, with a stronger focus on prioritisation and demonstrable impact. Agreement was reached on the approach to mid-term review preparation, including structured advance material and rehearsal sessions.

More broadly, the meeting enabled open and candid discussion of structural challenges within ELIXIR, particularly around improving cross-Platform collaboration, engagement with Communities and Science Tiers, and the balance between infrastructure development and user-facing impact. Early reflections on the 2029–2033 programme highlighted the importance of consultation design, structural clarity, and incentives that support meaningful collaboration rather than reinforce silos.

The outputs of this meeting will directly inform the finalisation of the 2027–2028 Commissioned Services, the June 2026 SAB mid-term review, and the consultation process for the next Scientific Programme.

Acknowledgements

We thank all ExCo members, ELIXIR Hub colleagues, Programme Managers, Science Officers, and Platform representatives for their active participation and constructive discussion. Their engagement was essential to consolidating strategic direction for the remainder of the 2024–2028 programme and preparing for the next phase of ELIXIR development